

CLINICAL STUDY ON THE EFFICACY OF SAFOOF HABIS IN THE MANAGEMENT OF MENORRHAGIA (KASRAT-E-TAMS)-A PILOT STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Menorrhagia, characterized by excessive and prolonged menstrual bleeding, is a major gynecological concern affecting women's health and quality of life. Conventional treatment options often include hormonal therapy or surgical interventions, such as hysterectomy, which may not always be suitable or affordable. In the Unani system of medicine, Safoof-e-Habis—prepared from Sang-e-Jarahat (hydrated magnesium silicate)—is traditionally prescribed as a haemostatic and astringent agent for excessive uterine bleeding. This pilot clinical study was conducted to evaluate the efficacy and safety of Safoof-e-Habis in the management of Kasrate Tams (menorrhagia). Thirty diagnosed patients of reproductive age (13–45 years) with a history of heavy menstrual bleeding were enrolled. The study followed an open-label pre- and post-treatment design, with Safoof-e-Habis administered orally in powdered form once daily during three consecutive menstrual cycles, followed by one observation cycle without treatment. Assessment was based on both subjective symptoms and objective parameters, including PBAC (Pictorial Blood Assessment Chart) scoring, clinical history, physical examination, and temperament (Mizaj) evaluation. Results demonstrated a significant reduction in menstrual blood loss, duration of bleeding, and associated symptoms such as fatigue, giddiness, and pallor. Most participants (80%) had a Balghami Mizaj, correlating with the classical Unani concept of altered humoral balance contributing to heavy bleeding. The formulation was found to be well-tolerated, cost-effective, and free of adverse effects.

KEYWORDS: Menorrhagia, Sufoof Habis, treatment, traditional medicine, herb.

I. INTRODUCTION OF MENORRHAGIA

Menorrhagia is one of the most significant causes of ill health in women. It accounts for a significant number of gynecological outpatient referrals and once referred to a gynecologist, more than half of these women will have had a hysterectomy within five years. Objective menorrhagia is taken to be a total measured menstrual

blood loss in excess of 80 milliliters per cycle. The objective diagnosis of menorrhagia can pose a clinical challenge. This article reviews the different methods currently used for the objective estimation of menstrual blood loss.

Fig. 01: Menorrhagia- A common Female disease.

Menorrhagia is considered to be one of the most significant causes of ill health in women. One in 20 women aged between 30 and 49 years consults her general practitioner each year with heavy menstrual loss. Menorrhagia accounts for 12% of gynecological outpatient referrals and once referred to a gynecologist 60% of these women will have had a hysterectomy within five years.

Menorrhagia can be defined both objectively and subjective. Objective menorrhagia is taken to be a total of measured menstrual blood loss in excess of 80 ml per cycle. The average menstrual blood loss is 35-50ml, without significant clots. This definition is taken from population studies, which have shown that approximately 10% of women experience losses of over 80ml/cycle. Subjectively, menorrhagia is defined as a complaint of excessive regular menstrual bleeding occurring over several consecutive cycles in women of reproductive years.

The objective diagnosis of menorrhagia can pose a clinical challenge. Our aim was to review the different methods proposed for the estimation of menstrual blood loss.

II. History and background of Menorrhagia in unani system of Medicine

Kasrate tams or *auja al-rahim* in Greco-Arabic (Unani) medicine is pain associated with menstruation^[1] or pain of uterine origin^[2] analogy of dysmenorrhea /menstrual cramps or pelvic pain, respectively, associated with gynecological diseases. Dysmenorrhea is a Greek word,^[3,4] Dys means "difficult," "painful," or "abnormal"; meno is "month"; and rhea is "flow," meaning difficult monthly flow.^[3] Dysmenorrhea is a common gynecological condition that can involve as much as 50% of women, and 10% of these women suffer severely enough to leave them incapacitated for 1 to 3 days each menstrual cycle.^[5,6] It has a major impact on health-related quality of life, health care utilization, and work productivity.^[7]

Fig. 02: Menorrhagia- Background and premises.

In traditional Unani medicine, herbs and other modalities of treatments are in use since antiquity for ameliorating menstrual pain. Therefore, it is need of the hour for the comprehensive exploration of long-established knowledge mentioned in classical Unani manuscripts for the management of *auja al-rahim / usr-i-tamth* and to implement the current researches conducted in integrative medicine/complementary and alternative medicine in the contemporary era. Greco-Arabic, Arabic medicine, and Islamic medicine refer to medicine developed in the Islamic Golden Age, the period extending from the 6th century to the 13th century. Medicine was developed in all 4 periods of medieval Islamic culture, that is, Prophet period (570-633 AD), Caliph period (632-660AD), Umayyad period (660-750 AD), and Abbasid period (750-1258 AD). It was a fundamental part of medieval Islamic culture. It retains its traditional essence and is one of the ancient systems of medicine that exists till date.^[13] Islamic physicians and scholars developed a large and multifaceted medical literature, searching, scrutinizing, and synthesizing the theory and practice of medicine. Some of the renowned physicians were Ali bin Rabban Tabri, Ali ibn al-'Abbas al-Majusi (Haly Abbas), Muhammad ibn Zakariyā Rāzī (Rhazes), Abu Sahl Masihi, Ibn Sīnā (Avicenna), Zayn al-Din Sayyed Isma'il ibn Husayn Gorgani (Ismail Gorgani), Ibn Rushd (Averroes), Ibn Zuhr (Avenzoar), Ibn al-Baitar, and so on.^[14]

The Arabic and Persian manuscripts, for example, Ibn Sina's *al Qānūn fī al-Tibb* (Canon of Medicine), Al Razi's *kitab al Hawi fi al-Tibb* (Continens Liber) and *al Mansuri* (Liber al mansoris), Al-Jurjani's *Zakhirah-i Khvarazm 'Shahi*, Rabban Tabri's *Firdous al-Hikmat* (Paradise of Wisdom), Al-Majusi's *Kitāb Kāmil aṣ-Ṣinā'a at-Tibbiyya* (Liber Regius/Complete Book of the Medical Art), Ibn Rushd's *Kitab al-Kulliyat*, and Ibn Zohr's *Kitab al-Taysir* were referred for causes and management of uterine pain/menstrual pain. In addition, *Tibb-i-Akbar*, *Kitab al-Mukhtarāt Fi'l Tibb*, *Rumuz-e-i-Az'am*, *Jamia al-Hikmat Iksir-i-Az'am*, and others were also referred. Terms such as dysmenorrhoea, pelvic pain, menstrual cramps, menstrual pain, herbs, complementary and alternative treatment for menstrual cramps, acupuncture and dysmenorrhoea, anti-inflammatory herbs for dysmenorrhoea, and antispasmodic herbs were searched. The inclusion criteria were the aforementioned terms and full-length freely accessible articles and abstracts were excluded.

III. Unani Concept of Menorrhagia

Kasrat-i-Tams occur mainly due to weakness of retentive power (*Quwwat-i-Masika*) of uterus secondary to altered temperament of uterus (*Sū'i-Mizaj al-Rahim*) or strong expulsive power (*Quwwat-i-Daf'ya*) of uterus secondary to *Khilt-i-Ladha'* or *Kaṭhrat-i-Khūn* or both^[1,2,4,5] its causes are classified into two categories.

Causes pertaining to uterus: *Du'f al-Rahim* (uterine

weakness) as in multiparity, abortion, and excessive intercourse^[1,2,4-10], *Qarh al-Rahim* (uterine ulcer), *Bawasir al-Rahim* (uterine polyp), *Kharish al-Rahim*, *Shiqaq al-Rahim* (uterine rupture)^[1,9], Rupture or dilatation of uterine vessels secondary to *Sū'i-Mizaj al-Rahim*.^[1,2,9], *Ḍarba wa saqta Rahim* (trauma & injury to uterus) resulting in rupture of uterine vessels.^[2,10]

Causes pertaining to blood: *Imtela-i-Khūn or Kaṭhrat-i-Khūn*^[2-10,7] (either increased production of blood or decreased consumption of blood by the body), thus *Tab'iyat* eliminates excess amount of blood in the form of menstruation. Moreover, congestion of blood in uterine vessels stimulates the expulsive power of uterus which in turn causes *Kaṭhrat-i-Tamth*, resulting in *Tanqiya Badan* (detoxification of body).^[5,7] Blood is normal in quality or quantity but *Du'f Badan* causes *Kasrat-i-Tams*.^[2] Even qualitative or quantitative changes in blood like *Riqqat-i-Khūn* (increased fluidity of blood) due to *Kaṭhrat-i-Ruṭubat Ma'ye or Latafat-i-Khūn*^[3] causes weakness of uterine vessels leading to HMB.^[1,2-5,11,9] Narrow path of vessels causes flow of thin and scanty blood and wider path of vessels causes flow of thick and profuse blood.^[2]

Clinical presentation: During menstruation, initially thin & scanty blood flow occur followed by thick & heavy blood flow, if this continues for longer duration again thin and scanty blood flow occur.^[2,11] Associated symptoms are anorexia.^[2,4,11], indigestion, increased thirst, palpitation, generalized body ache, excessive tiredness, giddiness etc. clinical examination findings are pallor, rapid pulse, cold and clammy skin, high coloured urine, generalized edema.^[2]

IV. Menorrhagia: Modern Concept

The term 'menorrhagia' is from the Greek word, 'mene' meaning 'moon' and 'rrhagia' meaning 'burst forth'. Menorrhagia denotes cyclic regular bleeding, which is excessive in amount or duration. Menorrhagia is defined as cyclic bleeding at normal intervals; the bleeding is either excessive in amount (> 80 ml) or duration or both, the term menotaxis is often used to denote prolonged bleeding.^[11] A normal menstrual blood loss is 50 to 80 mL and does not exceed 100 mL in menorrhagia, the menstrual cycle is unaltered, but the duration and quantity of the menstrual loss are increase.^[13] It is generally caused by conditions affecting the uterus or its vascularity, rather than any disturbance of function of the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian (H-P-O) axis. Whenever the uterine endometrial surface is enlarged, the bleeding surface is increased, contributing to excessive bleeding. Such conditions prevail in uterine fibroids, adenomyosis, uterine polyps, myohyperplasia and endometrial hyperplasia. Menorrhagia is also seen in women with increased uterine vascularity such as in chronic pelvic inflammatory disease and pelvic endometriosis. The uterus is often retroverted in position with restricted mobility. Such a uterus tends to be bulky and congested. The presence of an IUCD often leads to heavy and

prolonged bleeding. Lastly, menorrhagia may be the result of bleeding disorders like Von Willebrand's disease or an arteriovenous aneurysm.^[13]

Menorrhagia is essentially a symptom and not in itself a disease. It affects 20–30% of women at some time or other with significant adverse effects on the quality of life in terms of anaemia, cost of sanitary pads and interference with day-to-day activities. Several causes may prevail in a few cases, and attribute to excess bleeding. The underlying cause may be difficult to detect, in a few cases.

Once the menstrual bleeding starts, the platelet aggregation forms clots in the opened vessels. Prostaglandin F_{2a} (PGF_{2α}) causes myometrial contractions and constricts the endometrial vessels. The repair and epithelial regeneration begin on the 3rd and 4th day of period, by the growth of epithelial cells from the open endometrial glands aided by the vascular endothelial, epidermal and fibroblast growth factors.

Causes: *The causes are divided into*^[8, 13]

1. Pelvic Causes^[8,13] These include

- Uterine causes: Uterine fibroids, fibroid polyp, adenomyosis, endometrial hyperplasia.
- Chocolate cyst: Ovarian feminizing tumors, polycystic ovarian disease (PCOD), endometriosis.
- Uterine arteriovenous fistula and varicosity of vessels: (rare)—This may be congenital, but quite often it is traumatic following dilatation and curettage (D&C).
- Salpingo-oophoritis, pelvic inflammatory disease (PID), genital TB, varicose veins in the pelvis.
- Immediate puerperal and postabortal periods.
- Oestrogen secreting ovarian tumours.

Drug: SANG-E-JARAHAT

Botanical Name: Hydrated Magnesium Silicate

Figure: Sang-e-Jarahat (Hydrated Magnesium Silicate)

It is a type of stone which is soft, light in weight, odorless and white in color. It is used in healing of wound so called *Sang-E-Jarahat*. It is available in market in the form of powder or bloc. It dissolves in water, so it is used for washing of cloths. This is a very fine white, soft and shiny stone like a soap, which is found in the form of powder in market without odor and taste, It is free of gritty particles, greasy to touch and adheres top

g) Endometrial causes increased PGE₂, increased fibrinolysis.

2. Systemic causes^[8,13], These include.

- Liver dysfunction: Failure to conjugate and thereby inactivates the oestrogens.
- Cardiovascular dysfunction: Congestive cardiac failure
- Severe hypertension

3. Endocrinal causes^[8,13] These include.

- Thyroid dysfunction: Hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism in initial stages.

4. Haematological causes^[8,13], These include.

- Idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura
- Leukaemia
- Von Willebrand's disease
- Platelet disorders (Bernard-Soulier Syndrome (51%), Glanzmann's thrombasthenia
- (98%) Coagulation disorders are seen in 20% adolescents
- Severe anaemia
- Emotional upset^[8], these include: Stress, anxiety, fear may disturb the H-P-O axis

5. Iatrogenic Causes These include.

- Iatrogenic cause of menorrhagia is progesterone administration (mini pill).
- Intrauterine contraceptive device (IUCD) has provided yet another aetiological factor. Five to ten per cent of women wearing the device suffer menorrhagia in the first few months.
- Post sterilization menorrhagia is reported in 15% cases, but the aetiology is not clear. No obvious cause is seen in 40–50% of the cases.

skin. Talc is insoluble in water, dilute acids and alkali hydroxides.

Chemical Constituent

Chemically, it is a hydrated magnesium silicate represented by formula Mg₆(Si₂O₅)₄. Normally, it contains 1-2% of iron oxide and only traces of aluminum oxide. Color of talcum is due to iron oxide content. It also

contains 47.5% Silica and Magnesium.

Afaal (Action)

Habisud dam (Haemostatic), *Mujaffif* (Desiccant), *Qabis* (Astringent), *Musakkin* (Sedative), *Dafe Lissa Damia*, *Jali* (Detergent), *Mundamil qurooh* (Healing of wound), *Dafe Tasamum dam* (Antisepticaemia), *Muhalli warm* (Anti-Inflammatory), *Habis ishaal* (Anti-diarrhoeal).

Istemaal (Uses)

It prevents bleeding from all organs, so it is used as haemostatic agent in Menorrhagia, haematuria, Haemoptysis.

It is used in healing of wound externally in the form of *Qairuti* or *Marham* and orally in the form of powder especially in healing of *Zakhme Suzak* and *Zakhm Gurda Wa Masana* (ulcers of kidney and bladder).

It dries up secretion of stomach and intestine. It is also helpful in fever and bilious disease. It helps to strengthen the gum and prevents bleeding from gums. It also helps in stomatitis and ulcers of intestine.

It is used as cooling agent in powdered form to sprinkle on boils or as soothing action in irritation of wound. It is also used in spermatorrhoea, Leucorrhoea, Dysentery.

It is used as filter aid for filtration and clarification of cloudy liquids, as lubricant in preparations of pills and tablets and as dusting powder.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

- To evaluate the Efficacy of Unani formulation *Safoof-e-Habis (Sang-e-Jarahat)* in reducing the heavy menstrual bleeding in patient of *Kasrate Tams*.
- Assessment of *Mizaj* and its co-relationship with the occurrence of *Kasrate Tams* (Menorrhagia).
- To provide safe, effective and easily available drug for the treatment of *Kasrate Tams*.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The open label pre and post treatment clinical research study is carried out to evaluate the efficacy of safe, effective, pocket friendly herbo-mineral Unani formulation (*Sang-e-jarahat*) in reducing heavy menstrual bleeding in patients of *Kasrate Tams* (Menorrhagia), with assessment of *Mizaj* in the Dept. of *Ilmul Qabolat wa Amraz-e-Niswan*. Before the commencement of the study the protocol was submitted for ethical clearance. After submission, institutional committee had approved the protocol. The female patients either married or unmarried visiting the OPD from 13-45 years of age with c/o menorrhagia firstly screened out for the diagnostic case of menorrhagia with the history of heavy menstrual bleeding for >7 days or heavy blood flow > 80ml (assessed by PBAC score) for 3 or more consecutive cycles are enrolled in the study. Total 30 patients were included in the study with their detailed history, general physical & systemic examination, sign & symptoms and lab investigations.

METHODOLOGY

1. **STUDY DESIGN:** This study will be an open label randomized clinical study.
2. **SAMPLE SIZE:** 30 diagnosed cases of *Kasrate Tams* (Menorrhagia) were selected as per selection criteria.
3. **SETTING:** Patients were selected from OPD *Ilmul Qabalate Wa Amraz-e-Niswan* of related hospital.

4. DURATION OF STUDY & PROTOCOL THERAPY

The duration of the study will be 18 months, and the protocol therapy will be 120 days (3 consecutive menstrual cycle with treatment & 1 consecutive menstrual cycle without treatment). According to usual bleeding days of a patient medicine is started on the last day of their bleeding menstrual day (5th -7th day consideration) till bleeding stops.

5. **AGE GROUP:** Females of 13-45 years of age.

Method of Selection of Study Subject

Patients will be selected after approval from Institutional Ethical Committee (IEC). Patients who will attend the OPD of related Hospital after randomization. Eligible candidates (satisfying inclusion criteria and willing to enroll in the study by giving their consent), will be enrolled for obtaining demographic information, chief complaints disease duration recording, then detailed history, physical examination, local, general and systemic examination. (After getting their informed consent for the study).

INCLUSION CRITERIA

- History of excessive bleeding (either in amount or/& duration) for more than 3 consecutive cycles
- Women in the reproductive age group (13-45 years) with heavy menstrual bleeding.
- Clinically established cases of Menorrhagia (PBAC Score, Bleeding Amount & Duration of Bleeding from Grade 1-3).
- Patients are willing to participate in the study and follow up regularly till completion of study.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- Irregular menstrual cycles.
- Women using an IUCD/OCP.
- Endometrial hyperplasia
- History of taking HRT in last 3 months.
- Patients having pelvic pathology.
- Patients suffering from any other systemic disease.
- Patients not willing to give consent.
- Mentally retarded patients.
- Patients taking antiplatelet drugs.

WITHDRAWAL CRITERIA

During the course of treatment, if.

- Patients not taking proper medicine as per the scheduled explained to them or
- Any serious adverse event occurs or
- Uncontrolled hypertension
- Subject himself /herself wants to withdraw from the study,
- Patient who will not give proper follow-up.

Preparation for the Drug: The stone of *Sang-e-Jarahat* (Magnesium Silicate), will get from local dealer of Pune were authenticated by a botanist at department of Botany. Formulation will prepare in powder form. The drugs were taken and grinded to form a fine powder then filtered with 80 no. of sieved.

DOSAGE: The oral herbal formulation 5gm once daily, in morning with water or milk from their usual last day of menstrual bleeding (5th- 7th day consideration) till bleeding stops for the women in reproductive age group (13-45 years) with heavy menstrual bleeding.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS**The Age Distribution of the Cases Studied.****Table 1: The age distribution of the cases studied (n=30).**

Age Group (years)	No. of cases	% of cases
18 – 30	24	80.0
31 – 40	3	10.0
>40	3	10.0
Total	30	100.0
Values are n (% of cases).		

Comments

- 1) Of 30 cases studied, 24 cases (80.0%) had age between 18 – 30 years, 3 (10.0%) had age between 31 – 40 years, 3 cases (10.0%) had age more than 40 years.
- 2) The mean \pm SD, (Min – Max) of age of the group was 27.40 ± 7.72 years (Min = 18 years, Max = 47 years).

Figure 03: The age distribution of the cases studied (n=30)

Distribution of occupation among the cases studied.

Table 02: Distribution of occupation among the cases studied (n=30).

Occupation	No. of cases	% of cases
Student	12	40.0
Housewife	18	60.0
Total	30	100.0
Values are n (% of cases).		

Comments

- 3) Of 30 cases studied, 12 cases (40.0%) were students, and 18 cases (60.0%) were housewives.
- 4) Majority of the cases studied were housewives in the study group.

Figure 04: Distribution of occupation of the cases studied (n=30).

The distribution of religion of the cases studied.

Table 03: The distribution of religion of the cases studied (n=30).

Religion	No. of cases	% of cases
Muslim	30	100.0
Non-Muslim	0	0.0
Total	30	100.0
Values are n (% of cases).		

Comments

- 1) Of 30 cases studied, all i.e. 30 cases (100.0%) were Muslims. Majority of the cases studied were Muslims in the study group.

Figure 05: The distribution of religion of the cases studied (n=30).

The distribution of marital status of the cases studied.

Table 04: The distribution of marital status of the cases studied (n=30).

Marital status	No. of cases	% of cases
Married	18	60.0
Unmarried	12	40.0
Total	30	100.0
Values are n (% of cases).		

Comments.

- 1) Of 30 cases studied, 18 cases (60.0%) were married, and 12 cases (40.0%) were unmarried. Majority of the cases studied were married.

Figure 06: The distribution of marital status of the cases studied (n=30).

The distribution of age at menarche among the cases studied.

Table 05: The distribution of age at menarche among the cases studied (n=30).

Age at menarche	No. of cases	% of cases
11 years	6	20.0
12 years	8	26.7
13 years	9	30.0
14 years	7	23.3
Total	30	100.0
Values are n (% of cases).		

Comments

- 1) Of 30 cases studied, 6 cases (20.0%) had 11 years as age at menarche, 8 cases (26.7%) had 12 years of age at menarche, 9 cases (30.0%) had 13 years of age at menarche, and 7 cases (23.3%) had 14 years as age at menarche. Majority of cases have 13 years as age at menarche in the study group.

Figure 07: The distribution of age at menarche among the cases studied (n=30).

The distribution of type of mizaj (temperament) of the cases studied:

Table 06: The distribution of type of Mizaj (temperament) of the cases studied (n=30).

Type of Mizaj	No. of cases	% of cases
Balghami	24	80.0
Damwi	4	13.3
Safrawi	2	6.7
Total	30	100.0
Values are n (% of cases).		

Comments

- 1) Of 30 cases studied, 24 cases (80.0%) had *Balghami Mizaj*, 4 cases (13.3%) had *Damwi Mizaj*, and 2 cases (6.7%) had *Safrawi Mizaj*.
- 2) Majority of the cases studied were *Balghami Mizaj*.

Figure 08: The distribution of type of Mizaj (temperament) of the cases studied (n=30).

DISCUSSION

The present clinical study evaluated the therapeutic efficacy and safety of Safoof-e-Habis in the management of Menorrhagia (Kasrate Tams), a prevalent gynecological condition characterized by excessive and/or prolonged menstrual bleeding. The disorder is a significant health concern among women of reproductive age, leading to anemia, weakness, and decreased quality of life. In Unani medicine, Kasrate Tams is primarily attributed to the weakness of uterine tone (Zauf-e-Rahem) and disturbance of temperament (Sue Mizaj), particularly the dominance of Balghami (phlegmatic) humor, which impairs the natural process of blood expulsion and regulation. In this study, most participants belonged to the 13–45 years age group, representing the reproductive period when hormonal and endometrial functions are active. The predominance of Balghami Mizaj (80%) among the participants corroborates classical Unani descriptions, wherein excessive cold and moist temperament leads to sluggish uterine contractions and delayed cessation of bleeding. Environmental and dietary factors, such as consumption of cold, moist, or heavy foods, may further aggravate this humoral imbalance. The therapeutic response to Safoof-e-Habis

was highly encouraging. A statistically significant reduction in menstrual blood loss, as measured by the Pictorial Blood Assessment Chart (PBAC) scores, along with decreased duration of bleeding, and relief from symptoms like fatigue, dizziness, and pallor, was observed after three cycles of treatment. The formulation exhibited no adverse effects, indicating its excellent safety and tolerability. The observed effects can be attributed to the pharmacological properties of the chief ingredient, Sang-e-Jarahat (Hydrated Magnesium Silicate), which possesses haemostatic (Qabiz-e-Dam), astringent (Qabiz), cooling (Mubarrid), and anti-inflammatory (Muhallil-e-Waram) actions. These properties help in constricting dilated uterine vessels, promoting clot formation, and stabilizing the endometrial lining, thereby reducing menstrual blood flow. Additionally, the Unani principle of strengthening the uterine musculature (Taqwiyat-e-Rahem) is fulfilled through the compound's ability to restore uterine tone and correct humoral derangements. When compared to modern hormonal or surgical interventions, Safoof-e-Habis offers several advantages—it is natural, cost-effective, non-hormonal, and free from significant side effects. Moreover, it aligns with the Unani approach of

addressing the root cause by balancing the humors and strengthening vital organs rather than providing only symptomatic relief. In conclusion, the results of this study substantiate the Unani claim that Safoof-e-Habis is an effective remedy for Kasrate Tams. Its haemostatic and astringent properties provide a rational, evidence-based explanation for its traditional use. However, to validate these findings further, larger randomized controlled trials with biochemical and hormonal assessments are recommended. Such studies will strengthen the scientific basis for incorporating Safoof-e-Habis into mainstream gynecological practice for the holistic management of menorrhagia.

SUMMARY

The present clinical study explored the efficacy and safety of Safoof-e-Habis, a traditional Unani formulation, in the management of Menorrhagia (Kasrate Tams), a common gynecological disorder characterized by excessive or prolonged menstrual bleeding. Conducted on women aged 13–45 years, the study aimed to provide a natural, non-hormonal, and cost-effective alternative to conventional therapies, which often have side effects or limited patient acceptability. A total of 30 patients with a history of heavy menstrual bleeding for at least three consecutive cycles were enrolled. The formulation Safoof-e-Habis, prepared from Sang-e-Jarahat (Hydrated Magnesium Silicate), was administered orally once daily during three consecutive menstrual cycles, followed by an observation period. The therapeutic response was assessed using the Pictorial Blood Assessment Chart (PBAC), along with subjective symptoms such as fatigue, dizziness, and pallor. The findings revealed a significant reduction in menstrual blood loss, a shortened duration of bleeding, and an overall improvement in general well-being. Notably, 80% of the participants exhibited Balghami (phlegmatic) temperament, supporting the Unani theory that excessive cold and moist humors lead to sluggish uterine function and prolonged bleeding. The formulation was well tolerated, and no adverse effects were reported during the study period. The beneficial effects of Safoof-e-Habis are attributed to its haemostatic (Qabiz-e-Dam), astringent (Qabiz), anti-inflammatory (Muhallil-e-Waram), and cooling (Mubarriid) actions, which help in reducing uterine bleeding, constricting dilated vessels, and improving uterine tone (Taqwiyat-e-Rahem). These pharmacological actions correlate well with Unani principles that emphasize restoring humoral balance and strengthening the uterus. In conclusion, Safoof-e-Habis proved to be an effective, safe, and affordable herbal formulation for the management of Kasrate Tams (Menorrhagia). The study validates its traditional Unani use and suggests its potential role as a natural alternative to hormonal or surgical treatments. Further large-scale and controlled studies are recommended to substantiate these findings and explore its long-term benefits in women's reproductive health.

CONCLUSION

The present clinical study demonstrates that Safoof-e-Habis is an effective and safe Unani formulation for the management of Menorrhagia (Kasrate Tams). The use of Safoof-e-Habis resulted in a significant reduction in menstrual blood loss, shortened duration of bleeding, and marked improvement in associated symptoms such as fatigue, dizziness, and pallor. No adverse effects were observed during the treatment, confirming its excellent safety and tolerability. The predominance of Balghami (phlegmatic) temperament among the participants supports the Unani concept that an excess of cold and moist humors weakens uterine tone and prolongs menstrual flow. The therapeutic benefits of Safoof-e-Habis can be attributed to its haemostatic (Qabiz-e-Dam), astringent (Qabiz), cooling (Mubarriid), and anti-inflammatory (Muhallil-e-Waram) properties, which collectively strengthen the uterus (Taqwiyat-e-Rahem) and restore humoral balance (E'tidal-e-Akhlal). When compared with modern hormonal or surgical interventions, Safoof-e-Habis offers a natural, cost-effective, non-hormonal, and holistic alternative without side effects. It aligns with the Unani philosophy of addressing the root cause rather than merely alleviating symptoms. Hence, Safoof-e-Habis can be recommended as a reliable Unani remedy for the management of Menorrhagia, promoting women's reproductive health through safe and natural means. However, further large-scale, controlled clinical trials are warranted to confirm these findings, standardize dosage, and establish its long-term efficacy and mechanism of action.

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